

Shooting the Death Star: An Exploration of the Double Pendulum

CAS-522: Methods for Complex Systems Science—Dynamical Systems

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Introduction

TL;DR: Check out [Figure 2.4](#) and [Figure 2.7](#).

The double pendulum is perhaps one of the most classical examples there are of a chaotic dynamical system. As early as 1983, Richter and Scholz (1983) reported that this “simple classical textbook example displays all the complexity of non-integrable Hamiltonian systems.” It surely is the most accessible such system, being easily and affordably replicated on any tabletop. Yet while the 1980s roared with images of the Mandelbrot set, it appears that to the present day we have been waiting for a similar depiction of the behavior of the double pendulum, which turns out to give a beautiful fractal as well (Mandelbrot 1980).

This paper is structured into three sections that explore the double pendulum in the abstract and in application:

Chapter 1 lays the foundation by identifying an accurate and performant solver to integrate the double pendulum’s equations of motion numerically. We reproduce D’Alessio’s (2023) trajectory for the canonical $M = L = 1$ case.

Chapter 2 then proceeds to draw maps of the double pendulum’s divergence depending on initial conditions. These turn out to be gorgeous, and I have been unable to find any prior attempts at doing this other than a recent YouTube video I found as I started working on this project (2swap 2025).

Chapter 3 gives a delightful practical application of our ability to examine the double pendulum’s motion. I analyze the ‘Death Star,’ a target popular in the speed shooting sports, that obtains its fiendishly frustrating fluctuations from being a double pendulum. In order to do so, I first derive the equations of motion for a double pendulum with an arbitrary distribution of mass in the plane. I end with a recommendation on how to shoot this target most effectively.

1 Solving the Double Pendulum

As a first step, we want to explore numerical solution methods for the double pendulum. Famously, the double pendulum has no analytic solution and behaves chaotically for many initial states (Richter and Scholz 1983). We thus need to be sure that for the length of the time interval we integrate over, we get reliable solutions. We also want a speedy solution so that later on we can do trials with many iterations to explore the behavior of double-pendulum systems.

1.1 Equations of Motion

D'Alessio gives an easy-to-follow derivation of the equations of motion for the double pendulum (D'Alessio 2023).

First, he sets the problem up nondimensionally with:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau &= t\sqrt{g/\ell_1}, & (\cdot)' &\equiv \frac{d}{d\tau} \\ L &\equiv \ell_2/\ell_1, & M &\equiv m_2/m_1\end{aligned}$$

for ℓ_1 being the length of the inner and ℓ_2 being the length of the outer pendulum rod, m_1 and m_2 being the masses of the respective bobs, and g being gravitational acceleration. This gives the equations of motion

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_1' &= U, & \theta_2' &= V, \\ \theta_1'' &= \frac{M \sin \Delta (LV^2 + \cos \theta_2) + M \sin \Delta \cos \Delta U^2 - \sin \theta_1}{1 + M \sin^2 \Delta}, \\ \theta_2'' &= -\frac{1}{L} \left(\sin \theta_2 + \sin \Delta U^2 + \cos \Delta \theta_1'' \right), & \Delta &\equiv \theta_2 - \theta_1.\end{aligned}$$

with θ_1 and θ_2 being the deflections of the inner and outer rod, respectively, from the vertical. To check our work, it will be useful also to write down the dimensionless energy in the system

Figure 1.1: Double pendulum example

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{E} &= E/(m_1 g \ell_1), \\ \hat{T}(\theta_1, \theta_2, U, V) &= \frac{1}{2}(1 + M)U^2 + \frac{1}{2}ML^2V^2 + MLUV\cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1), \\ \hat{V}(\theta_1, \theta_2) &= (1 + M)(1 - \cos\theta_1) + ML(1 - \cos\theta_2), \\ \hat{E} &= \hat{T} + \hat{V}.\end{aligned}$$

This is, of course, preserved in our pendulum as long as we're not introducing friction into the system, and deviations will become a metric for numerical imprecision.

The accompanying code implements these equations of motion. We can see credible example output of a double-pendulum motion in Figure 1.1 ($m_1 = 1$ kg, $m_2 = 1$ kg, $\ell_1 = 1$ m, $\ell_2 = 1$ m, $\theta_1 = 90.0^\circ$, $\theta_2 = 135.0^\circ$, $t_{end} = 8$ s).

This is visually a close match to the output given by D'Alessio for the same parameter set (D'Alessio 2023, 17).

1.2 Convergence of Results

The common solvers with adaptive step size such as provided in `scipy.integrate.solve_ivp()` accept tolerance parameters for local errors. We now explore the relationship of the `atol`

parameter, making this one dominate `rtol`, to the accuracy of results and required number of function evaluations. We also add the simple Euler method as a comparison point, in this case varying the step size directly instead of the `atol` for the more advanced solvers with adaptive step sizes.

We evaluate for $m_1 = 5$ kg, $m_2 = 20$ kg, $\ell_1 = 1$ m, $\ell_2 = 0.3$ m, $\theta_1 = 90^\circ$, $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$, $t_{end} = 300$ s. This setup is close enough to the edges of chaos that we expect computational errors to be amplified without being so chaotic as for convergence to become hopeless. For error metrics, we look at the preservation of non-dimensional energy and at the difference of both θ_1 and θ_2 from the values generated by a run using the DOP853 method run with `atol`= 10^{-14} :

$$\epsilon_{\hat{E}} = \max_{0 \leq k \leq N-1} \left| \ln \frac{\hat{E}(t_k)}{\hat{E}(t_0)} \right|,$$

$$\epsilon_{\theta} = \max_{1 \leq i \leq 2} \max_{0 \leq k \leq N-1} |\theta_i(t_k) - \theta_{i,\text{ref}}(t_k)|.$$

Since our frictionless double pendulum preserves energy, we know that any value of $\epsilon_{\hat{E}}$ is pure numerical error from our evaluation and this should be kept to a value we consider negligible for our purpose, while ϵ_{θ} may be influenced by both numerical error and chaotic behavior, but should remain at a level significantly below the precision we expect to make claims about the pendulum’s behavior. In all cases we evaluate for output of 10^5 equidistant time steps.

We have a non-stiff problem that we want to solve close to machine precision so as to be able to distinguish the chaotic effects of changes in initial conditions from the chaotic effects of numerical imprecision. The SciPy documentation recommends DOP853 Dormand-Prince 8(5,3) for this purpose, so we’d hope that this will show both the best and also practicable performance. The BDF method is a specialist for stiff problems, so we expect it to carry a significant performance penalty, while LSODA automatically switches methods, which may be competitive, except when the problem is misdiagnosed as stiff (SciPy Developers 2025).

Figure 1.2 and Figure 1.3 show the results. As we expected, DOP853 performs reliably well. Under some circumstances, LSODA gives quicker answers for the same accuracy requirement, but with unpredictable swings perhaps attributable to LSODA’s method switching when a problem appears stiff. We thus conclude that DOP853 is indeed the preferred method, at least within SciPy’s toolkit, to solve double-pendulum-like problems. The Euler method, as we could expect, showed itself to be totally computationally ineffective for this sort of problem.

1.3 Speeding Things up

Having found (according to what we expected) a good solution algorithm for double pendulum integrations, we would now like to improve performance so that we can explore behaviors over

(a) Energy error

(b) Theta error

(c) Number of evaluations

(d) Time elapsed

Figure 1.2: Performance comparison of various ODE solvers

Figure 1.3: Accuracy and time needed of various ODE solvers

large parameter sets. Tests were run with the same parameter set as for the evaluation of algorithms, and with an `atol` of 10^{-12} .

`numbakit-ode` provides the DOP853 algorithm with events in an interface very similar to SciPy, but allows us to take advantage of Numba’s just-in-time compilation without incurring the cost of an intermediate Python function call for each evaluation and thus also without needing to acquire Python’s Global Interpreter Lock (Grecco and contributors 2025). Unfortunately, despite the benefits of just-in-time compilation, I obtained performance that is slower than that of SciPy’s apparently highly tuned method.

A simpler approach was to keep `scipy.integrate.solve_ivp`, but to run it with the double-precision math compiled by Numba (Lam, Pitrou, and Seibert 2015). This works, with a performance gain of about one quarter—not earth-shattering, but a simple improvement that requires nothing more than a function decorator.

NumbaSODA with a Numba-compiled function brought a significant speed increase of about five-fold compared to `solve_ivp`, but at the cost of needing a Fortran installation to compile and of running into a hard-coded limitation on the number of evaluation steps that does not work very well for the double-pendulum problem that has a simple system of equations, but needs a lot of steps for a good solution (Wogan 2025).

We will thus stick for simplicity with `solve_ivp` using the DOP853 algorithm.

2 Mapping the Double Pendulum

Despite its fame for chaotic behavior, there appears to be a scarcity of visual explorations of the double pendulum’s chaotic tendencies, certainly compared to the coffee-table books with depictions of the Mandelbrot set, *etc.* This scarcity is perhaps owing to the higher computational cost of solving the double pendulum, despite its intuitive appeal as a simple mechanical system easily demonstrated on a tabletop. Apparently the first display of some map was developed by Heyl (2008) in 2006 and published as a preprint in 2008, with the time to first flip being shown on a map for initial angles of the pendulum arms. This chart appeared in a number of additional articles (*e.g.*, Bender et al. 2009; Parker, Goluskin, and Vasil 2021). Recently, we have seen some more beautifully done illustrations on YouTube (2swap 2025). There clearly and perhaps surprisingly is space for refinement of visual presentations of the double pendulum map, ideally insightful and/or visually attractive.

We now want to create a map of the double pendulum’s tendency to become chaotic depending on θ_1 and θ_2 .

2.1 Choice of Divergence Criterion

The first question we face is what metric to use for chaotic behavior. Heyl (2008) uses time to the first time the pendulum flips over, *i.e.*, when $\theta_1 = \pi$ or $\theta_2 = \pi$. This is useful, but has its limits as a measure of chaos. Heyl shows that energetically the pendulum cannot possibly flip unless $3 \cos \theta_1 + \cos \theta_2 \leq 2$. As we will see, chaotic behavior is possible without the pendulum being able to flip while, conversely, enough energy to flip the pendulum does not ensure chaotic behavior.

An obvious measure of chaotic behavior would be the system’s highest Lyapunov exponent as examined for individual cases, but not arranged in a map, by D’Alessio (2023) and earlier authors (Shinbrot et al. 1992; Levien and Tan 1993). However, this seems impractical for both theoretical and practical reasons. Practically, the authors estimating Lyapunov exponents find that “convergence was observed to be slow,” end up using computationally expensive algorithms, and engage in somewhat arbitrary cutoffs (D’Alessio 2023).

The practical difficulties might be related to a theoretical problem. Lyapunov’s exponents are defined as the exponents of exponentially growing separation between two paths starting with a small separation in the limit as time goes to infinity. However, while the differences in angles produced by our equations of motion in polar coordinates may in principle grow to infinity,

Figure 2.1: Divergence of select double pendula

any difference between two angles that is a multiple of 2π is not a difference at all, but rather describes the system, unaware of its history as it is, in the exact same condition.

If we consider the growth in spatial separation between two double-pendulum bobs starting in almost the same position, the growth of separation between these two cannot possibly be exponential as time goes to infinity. (It is a general rule of finite systems that growth is exponential only until it isn't, with applications especially in finance and other social prediction.)

Rather, the separation is limited to at most twice the pendulum's length, and that only for the starting condition of $\theta_1 = \pi$ and $\theta_2 = \pi$, assuming no kinetic energy is present at the start. Similarly, the separation of speeds can also not diverge to a larger difference than the maximum speed permitted by the system's original energy content. Hence, the Lyapunov exponent as time goes to infinity cannot be meaningful and local Lyapunov exponents obtained depend primarily on the choice of cutoff points.

Therefore, we start our exploration by examining the patterns of how an initially small difference in the position of the outer bobs of two double pendula starting at very slightly displaced positions grows with time, and we will select a good metric of divergence and thus chaotic behavior from there. For all of our double pendula here we will, for simplicity and to reproduce others, work in dimensionless quantities and assume $M = L = 1$ (e.g., $\ell_1 = \ell_2 = 1$ m and $m_1 = m_2 = 1$ kg and, for $\tau = t \times 1/s$, $g = 1$ m/s²) and solve using DOP853 for both double pendula paths in one go.

Figure 2.1 shows the divergence of various double pendula from a small initial displacement of $\epsilon_{\theta_2} = 10^{-6}$. The divergence is given as Euclidean distance in terms of ℓ_1 . Since, due to a pendulum's swinging, divergences in space will increase and reduce, we are showing the maximal displacement achieved until a given time.

We see that there are cases that exhibit very rapid exponential growth of the error, cases that do not exhibit such exponential growth, at least within the examined time frame, and some borderline cases that exhibit slow exponential growth. Thus, we can neatly distinguish chaotic and non-chaotic behavior for many cases. As is to be expected, with limited computational resources and thus both a limited maximal time we are running to and limited numerical precision, there may be a few cases where the exponential growth and thus chaotic behavior exist, but are so slow that we are not able to distinguish them safely from non-chaotic behavior—and a real-world experiment subject to friction would also not distinguish them. As is clear from the pendulum by definition being tied in space, the divergence’s exponential growth eventually is bound to stop, at which point the two pendula just move in unrelated ways.

From this behavior, we can conclude that a reasonable measure of chaotic behavior may be a finite-time divergence measure of $\log \tau$ when the divergence of the two originally slightly displaced pendulum bobs, in Euclidean distance, first crosses a threshold that is large enough to integrate over a reasonably long time, but small enough to avoid getting into the constraint of the two bobs not being able to separate any further, *e.g.*, to a separation of 10^{-2} , or a somewhat smaller value to save time when achievement of a large separation would take an undue amount of time.

2.2 Divergence Maps

Now it is time to map divergence over the extent of the phase space we are interested in, on a reasonably tight grid of initial displacement angles, assuming no velocity, *i.e.*, dropping the bob from rest, in all cases, to keep the number of dimensions manageable and to limit ourselves to what would be easy to reproduce experimentally. We sample $(\theta_1, \theta_2) \in [-\pi, \pi]^2$ over an 1800×1800 grid ($\Delta\theta = 0.2^\circ$), taking advantage of the symmetry whereby (θ_1, θ_2) is equivalent to $(-\theta_1, -\theta_2)$ to halve our workload.

Figure 2.2 shows a selection of divergence growth paths for various double pendula from the entire phase space, with only the times needed for the initial error to grow by a power of ten plotted. We still see mostly a bifurcation into regimes of very rapid and very slow growth of errors with a minority population in between these two extremes, right at the edge of chaos.

Figures 2.3–2.5 show maps of the double pendulum’s divergence depending on initial conditions.

We can make a few observations:

- Starting at 100-fold divergence, one can see a clear outline of the lenticular area with $3 \cos \theta_1 + \cos \theta_2 \geq 2$ where the pendulum cannot flip, matching the shape shown in Heyl (2008, 3). As makes intuitive sense, the pendulum’s ability to flip greatly increases the chance of chaotic behavior.

Figure 2.2: Divergence of many double pendula

Time to 10-fold divergence

Figure 2.3: Time to 10-fold divergence map

Time to 100-fold divergence

Figure 2.4: Time to 100-fold divergence map

Figure 2.5: Time to n -fold divergence maps

- However, the pendulum's ability to flip is neither necessary nor sufficient for chaotic behavior. We see strands of chaos reach into the no-flip area, and we see areas of stability where there is enough energy for the pendulum to flip.
- Assuming that there is an area where the pendulum will never go chaotic (which is not proven from our numerical experiment other than for the trivial case of the pendulum at rest), as shown by the white areas in the plots, it probably has fractal borders. If there is such an area, is it contiguous?
- There is a difference between chaotic evolutionary dynamics and unstable equilibrium in initial conditions. In Figure 2.3 we can see a well-delineated river passing through starting conditions with the inner rod pointing straight up or down and the outer rod pointing straight up. Obviously, if these configurations are met exactly, we have an unstable equilibrium where our small perturbations will throw the pendulum either to the left or to the right, resulting in paths of motion that will be mirror images of each other. However, in Figure 2.4 as well as for the higher error thresholds, we see that the early divergence through most of that river of instability does not actually grow and propagate over time. So clearly, chaotic dynamics over time are a different mechanism from mere instability inherent in initial conditions.

The difference between instability in original conditions and chaotic dynamics already was apparent in Figures 2.1 and 2.2. We see that there appear to be two separate dynamics of initial, slow growth of the original perturbation, followed by a breakout into chaos at different times later. Hence many of the curves showing growth of the original perturbation appear to be parallel to each other, but shifted in the time axis. We may illustrate this more clearly by showing the growth from Figure 2.1 on a log-log-scale, without making any claim of a physical foundation for a functional form of the growth of error, as shown in Figure 2.6.

This plot suggests that we could detect separately the initial instability of the pendulum setup and the time when the dynamics enter chaotic behavior. It appears that for the cases with

Figure 2.6: Divergence of select double pendula (log-log)

chaotic breakout, one might obtain a good fit by a logistic curve in log-log space of the form

$$\log \epsilon(\tau) = \log \epsilon_0 + \frac{\log \epsilon_\infty - \log \epsilon_0}{1 + \exp(-k(\log \tau - \log \tau_a))}$$

with ϵ_0 being the given initial divergence, ϵ_∞ being the maximum divergence attainable by the constraints of pendulum length and energy, and τ_a and k being shaping parameters to be estimated that stand for the time to breakout and the speed of breakout. For our purposes, however, we can leave it at a simpler mechanism and just use the time to tenfold increase of the error as a measure of initial instability and time to hundredfold increase as a measure of chaotic dynamics. Mapping this to an RGB color space, we've got one color left, and we use time to 10,000-fold increase for that. This yields the very pretty plot in Figure 2.7.

An obvious next step would be to extend our investigation to different values of M and L and to zoom in on interesting parts to explore fractal behavior. Does the area of stability appear to be contiguous and what are the most extreme values for which stability exists? Is stability even categorically different from chaos, or are configurations that appear stable just taking a very long time to become chaotic? Equally interestingly, one could pick one energy content of the system (since absent friction states with different energy contents are not reachable from one another), most tantalizingly with the energy just sufficient to flip the pendulum over, and examine the resulting three-dimensional Poincaré sections. It is, however, time to move on for now.

Divergence of Double Pendulum

Figure 2.7: Chaotic behavior of the double pendulum

3 Shooting the Death Star

Now we would like to examine the dynamics of the double pendulum in the context of a fun application from the speed shooting sports, a chaotically swinging target called the Death Star. Before we get to specialized application, however, we need to generalize our double pendulum beyond the usual assumptions of massless rods and point-mass bobs.

3.1 Generalizing the Double Pendulum

3.1.1 Setup

Since the Death Star is a construction swinging in a plane, we can retain our two-dimensional coordinates, but we now have distributed (and eventually changing) masses as well as friction. We can characterize any shape swinging like a pendulum around a fixed pivot point in a gravity field sufficiently by $(m; I; x; y)$, with m being the mass, I being the mass moment of inertia around the center of mass, and x and y the position of the center of mass when the pivot point is in the origin and the rotation $\theta = 0$. We also add viscous damping coefficients $c^{(\text{dim})}$ for the bearings.

Angles are absolute with $\theta = 0$ pointing straight down, as in the earlier sections of this paper and taken over from D'Alessio (2023); gravity acts along $-\hat{y}$. Each rotor is described by (m, I, x, y) , where m is the mass, I is the mass moment about the link's COM (out of plane), and (x, y) are the world coordinates of the COM when the link hangs at $\theta = 0$, with x to the right and y downward.

We can now connect two such masses to form a double pendulum characterized by the five parameters mentioned above for each of the two pendulum halves, plus a parameter ℓ for distance of the second pivot point from the first, which we take to be located at $x = 0; y = -\ell$ when $\theta = 0$. Adding g as our gravitational acceleration, we now have twelve parameters that can describe the setup of any double pendulum in the plane, including viscous damping.

3.1.2 Equations of motion

As before, we scale out all units first and then work only with dimensionless quantities.

$$A := I_1 + m_1(x_1^2 + y_1^2) + m_2 \ell^2, \quad \tau^* := m_2 g \ell, \quad T^* := \sqrt{\frac{A}{\tau^*}},$$

Dimensionless time and parameters with time scale T^* :

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \frac{t}{T^*}, \quad (\cdot)' = \frac{d(\cdot)}{d\tau}, \\ B &= \frac{I_2 + m_2(x_2^2 + y_2^2)}{A}, \\ \kappa &= \frac{m_2 \ell^2}{A}, \\ \alpha &= \frac{m_1}{m_2}, \\ \xi_1 &= \frac{y_1}{\ell}, \quad \eta_1 = \frac{x_1}{\ell}, \\ \xi_2 &= \frac{y_2}{\ell}, \quad \eta_2 = \frac{x_2}{\ell}, \\ c_i &= c_i^{(\text{dim})} \frac{T^*}{A} \quad (i = 1, 2). \end{aligned}$$

Angles are absolute: θ_1, θ_2 ; let $\Delta = \theta_2 - \theta_1$.

We define the cross-inertia factor:

$$C(\Delta) = \kappa(\xi_2 \cos \Delta - \eta_2 \sin \Delta).$$

The kinetic energy is:

$$K = \frac{1}{2}(\theta_1'^2 + B \theta_2'^2) + C(\Delta) \theta_1' \theta_2',$$

The potential energy, up to an arbitrary constant, is:

$$U = \alpha(\eta_1 \sin \theta_1 - \xi_1 \cos \theta_1) - \cos \theta_1 + \eta_2 \sin \theta_2 - \xi_2 \cos \theta_2$$

The total energy (not including dissipated heat from friction) is:

$$E = K + U.$$

To write the equations of motion, we define the derivatives:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1} &= \kappa(\xi_2 \sin \Delta + \eta_2 \cos \Delta), \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_2} &= -\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1}, \\ G_1 &= \alpha(\eta_1 \cos \theta_1 + \xi_1 \sin \theta_1) + \sin \theta_1, \\ G_2 &= \eta_2 \cos \theta_2 + \xi_2 \sin \theta_2. \end{aligned}$$

In matrix form, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_1'' + C\theta_2'' + \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_2}\right)\theta_2'^2 + G_1 + c_1\theta_1' - c_2(\theta_2' - \theta_1') &= T_1, \\ C\theta_1'' + B\theta_2'' + \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1}\right)\theta_1'^2 + G_2 + c_2(\theta_2' - \theta_1') &= T_2.\end{aligned}$$

To get explicit ODEs for our solver, we define

$$\begin{aligned}h_1 &= \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_2}\right)\theta_2'^2, & h_2 &= \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1}\right)\theta_1'^2, \\ R_1 &= T_1 - c_1\theta_1' + c_2(\theta_2' - \theta_1') - G_1 - h_1, \\ R_2 &= T_2 - c_2(\theta_2' - \theta_1') - G_2 - h_2, \\ \Delta_M &= B - C^2.\end{aligned}$$

and then have:

$$\theta_1'' = \frac{BR_1 - CR_2}{\Delta_M}, \quad \theta_2'' = \frac{-CR_1 + R_2}{\Delta_M}.$$

The energy balance is

$$\frac{dE}{d\tau} = T_1\theta_1' + T_2\theta_2' - c_1\theta_1'^2 - c_2(\theta_2' - \theta_1')^2.$$

and, thus, with the external torques $T_i = 0$ and $c_i = 0$, energy is conserved, and with $c_i > 0$ friction dissipates energy and damps the system.

3.1.3 Numerical implementation

We have implemented a solver for this generic double pendulum using the same DOP853 solver with $atol = 10^{-12}$ and $rtol = 10^{-10}$ as we used previously. Figure 3.1 shows a reproduction of the example without friction in D'Alessio (2023), which matches, as well as the same pendulum with two levels of viscous friction.

3.2 The Double Pendulum Applied: The Death Star

3.2.1 Setup

The ‘Death Star’ is a moving target used in action shooting sports like USPSA and 3-Gun that exploits the chaotic dynamics of a double pendulum to create a fiendish challenge for the shooter. The inner arm of the double pendulum is a normal rod, and the outer arm is

Double pendulum trajectory damped and undamped

Figure 3.1: Double pendulum trajectory damped and undamped

arranged as a five-spiked star of arms that hold a steel plate in place by a spring mechanism. The starting position is with all five plates present and the inner arm around the vertical.

The shooter activates the target, typically by shooting yet another steel target that via a pulley mechanism removes a rod that props up the pendulum's inner arm. Then the task is to shoot off all five steel plates. For the first plate that is relatively simple as the outer star is still a balanced wheel and thus will not rotate much (and would not rotate at all if it was perfectly balanced and the bearing was frictionless). As soon as the first plate is shot off, however, the star is out of balance and the chaotic motion of a double pendulum begins, sometimes with the star picking up a great deal of speed. Figure 3.2 shows the arrangement.

The parts are made from abrasion-resistant steel and thus fairly heavy. An example of a shooter engaging this target may be seen at Forward Assist (2023).

From manufacturer's measurements and observation of the dynamics, I assume the dimensions in Table 3.1. The entire arrangement thus weighs 90 kg. The mass assumed for the outer arms includes an allowance for the bearing and mounting weight.

Figure 3.2: Arrangement of the Death Star shooting target

Dimension	Value
Inner arm length	0.7 m
Inner arm mass	15 kg
Outer arms length	0.5 m
Outer arms mass, each	12 kg
Plates radius	0.1 m
Plates mass, each	3 kg
Dimensionless coefficient of friction, inner	0.3
Dimensionless coefficient of friction, outer	0.3

Table 3.1: Death Star Dimensions

The file `death_star_dynamics.mp4` accompanying this paper shows an example of the behavior of the Death Star with one plate removed.

3.2.2 Shooter strategies

In solving this shooting problem, the shooter comes with certain preconditions about his skills that he cannot trivially change, and he has a choice of strategies how to work the problem. The question then is for the optimal strategy given preconditions.

We model shooting the Death Star as a cycle of observation and action. The shooter observes the swinging Death Star. Before each shot—and during recovery from the previous one—the shooter waits a certain time. Then the shooter has a choice to make. If the plates are moving too quickly, the shooter may elect to wait and observe some more instead of firing. We assume that the shooter uses the plates’ speed in Cartesian coordinates for this judgment. If the shooter elects to fire, he will pick a target among the plates and fire at it, holding to compensate for the target’s motion. Again, we assume that he holds by extrapolating from the plate’s current position and speed, but that he is not able to take the plate’s acceleration into account. This assumption may not be entirely realistic, especially in phases when the Death Star swings in a reasonably harmonic manner. However, we can reasonably hope that allowing the shooter also to estimate, *e.g.*, circular paths, would mostly shift our results on the shooter speed axis without changing them fundamentally.

For the shooter’s decision to pick a plate to shoot at, we model seven methods:

- random: the shooter picks any available plate
- topmost: the shooter shoots at the highest plate, perhaps in the hope to remove the most potential energy from the system

- bottommost: the shooter shoots at the lowest plate
- slowest: the shooter shoots at the slowest-moving plate, perhaps in the hope that it will be easiest to hit
- fastest: the shooter shoots at the fastest-moving plate, perhaps in the hope of removing the most kinetic energy from the system
- balance: the shooter picks a plate that will move the center of gravity closer to the star’s rotation point, *i.e.*, if plate 1 is missing, the shooter will shoot at plate 3 or 4, but not 2 or 5; if more than one plate is eligible under this rule, the shooter picks a plate among the eligible ones at random
- unbalance: opposite of balance

Between the shooter’s decision to fire and impact on the plate, a certain time elapses from reaction time, weapon lock time, and bullet flight time—these games are typically shot with subsonic pistol ammunition, so for typical distances the bullet will spend something like a thirtieth of a second in flight. The shooter will also introduce a certain error in his shot and not hit exactly where intended, which we model as normally distributed with a given standard deviation.

In order to keep the number of variables manageable, we assign a general speed rating to the shooter and say that the time to recover and think after each shot is 0.8 times the speed rating, and the time between firing at a target and impact is 0.2 times the speed rating; if the shooter elects to wait, that delay is 0.1 times the speed rating. (We use ‘speed’ colloquially for time per shot cycle, the inverse of shooting speed proper.)

Thus, a shooter’s skill is characterized by his speed rating and by his accuracy, the standard deviation of his shots. The shooter’s strategy is characterized by the speed threshold beyond which a plate must be moving for the shooter to consider firing at it instead of waiting and by one of the seven methods by which he can pick plates.

Whereas for our construction of the double-pendulum map we cared about divergent behavior, now we consider shooter performance. Actual scoring methods in the sports using this target can be complicated, so I devised a simple method that should correlate well with results in actual competition: the shooter’s performance is the time he needed, subject to a timeout at 120 seconds, plus a penalty of 1 second for each missed shot (even if no formal penalty is assessed, reloads cost time, and a shot count out of sync with stage planning forces unfavorable reloads later in the stage) and 20 seconds for each plate not removed. Less, of course, is better.

3.2.3 Monte-Carlo procedure

For each cell of shooter speed, accuracy, maximum acceptable plate speed, and plate selection method, we run an adaptive Monte-Carlo: initial angles $\theta_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(\pi/2, 3^\circ)$, $\theta_2 \sim \text{Unif}[0, 2\pi)$; each trial follows a wait–speed–lock cycle with durations $(0.8, 0.1, 0.2) \cdot \text{shooter_speed}$; at lock the aim is perturbed by i.i.d. Gaussian noise with per-axis $1\sigma = \text{accuracy}$ (m); plates

with center speed $> \text{max_speed}$ are skipped; dynamics use DOP853 with $\text{rtol} = 10^{-7}$, $\text{atol} = 10^{-9}$; a trial ends when all plates are cleared or at a 120 s timeout; the score is $p = t + \max(S - 5, 0) \cdot 1 + r \cdot 20$ s. We run ≥ 100 trials, then check every 25; stop when the last three checks meet both $\Delta \bar{p} \leq \max(0.005, 0.25\% \cdot \bar{p}_{\text{prev}})$ and $\Delta s_p \leq \max(0.005, 2\% \cdot s_{p,\text{prev}})$, capped at 1000 trials. Parameter grids and methods are as in Table 3.2; runs are parallelized across CPU cores with deterministic per-trial seeds. We have chosen looser tolerance here than for our previous explorations since we don't care about an exact characterization of divergent behavior at a specific spot, the initial conditions being randomized anyhow.

Aspect	Setting
Initial angles	$\theta_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(\pi/2, 3^\circ)$, $\theta_2 \sim \text{Unif}[0, 2\pi)$
Cycle timings	$(t_{\text{wait}}, t_{\text{speed}}, t_{\text{lock}}) = (0.8, 0.1, 0.2) \cdot \text{shooter_speed}$ s
Aim error	i.i.d. per-axis Gaussian, $1\sigma = \text{accuracy}$ m
Acceptance rule	Skip plate if center speed $> \text{max_speed}$
Integrator	DOP853, $\text{rtol} = 10^{-7}$, $\text{atol} = 10^{-9}$
Trial limit	Success or 120 s timeout
Scoring	$p = t + \max(S - 5, 0) \cdot 1 + r \cdot 20$ s, where t is the final time, S is the total number of shots fired, and r is the number of plates remaining.
Stopping	≥ 100 trials; check every 25; stall thresholds as above; max 1000
Parameter grids	$\text{shooter_speed} = 0.5 \cdot 2^{k/3}$ ($k=0\dots 12$); $\text{accuracy} = 0.01 \cdot 2^{k/2}$ ($k=0\dots 9$) m; $\text{max_speed} = 0.01 \cdot 2^{k/2}$ ($k=0\dots 19$) m/s; $\text{methods} = \{\text{topmost, bottommost, slowest, fastest, random, balance, unbalance}\}$

Table 3.2: Monte-Carlo Parameter Grid

3.2.4 Results: What does it take?

Figure 3.3 shows the best performance available for shooters of various skill combinations in terms of speed and accuracy. For each combination of speed and accuracy, we selected the strategy, comprising maximum plate speed a shooter is willing to engage and plate selection, that gives the best results. The numbers shown are then shooter performance expressed as a time of time needed plus penalties. Everything above 100 s is atrocious since with our definition of a penalty of 20 s per missed plate the shooter would be better off simply surrendering, if needed by firing five rounds in the direction of the spinning Death Star quickly to avoid failure-to-engage penalties.

A monoski instructor (who was also a BASE jumper...) once described to me that the learning curve for the game he teaches is not so much a learning curve, but a learning cliff. We see that the same is true for shooting the Death Star. There is a zone of shooter speeds up to 0.8 s for

Figure 3.3: Best strategy performance for shooters of various skills

the shot cycle, thus by our definition 0.16 s reaction time between locking onto a target's speed and impact, and accuracy of a standard deviation of up to 6 cm where results are competitive. Within that zone there's a well-behaved tradeoff of speed and accuracy. On the wrong side of the learning cliff, however, with accuracy or speed below the minimum skill required to succeed in this game, attainable performance drops off sharply as time needed for completion increases drastically. For the following, we will only consider shooter speeds up to 2 s, since anyone slower needs to work on his speed first to avoid a truly frustrating performance.

For accuracy, the cliff shape of the learning curve has an obvious reason. As long as the shooter is likely to hit a plate, it does not matter whether he hits it in the center or toward the edge. (We assumed in our model equal effectiveness of hitting at each spot. In practice, there may be combinations of intentionally weak ammunition for the lowest recoil and strong springs holding the plate where hits toward the edges or on the edge may not make the plate fall. Our results should still hold, just with a shift in the accuracy scale.) For speed, the increase in shooter wait time from one shot to committing to the next, which we set at 0.8 times the shooter speed, should for the most part scale the time attained only linearly (except when it makes it impossible to take advantage of a time window when the wheel spins slowly). Thus, the main effect must come from the time set to 0.2 times the shooter speed between deciding shot placement and impact as the plate moves away from its linear trajectory.

The times we showed above were the ones attainable for a shooter of a given skill combination assuming optimal choice of strategy regarding selection of targets and holding one's fire when the plates are moving too fast. For a first glimpse at what the optimal strategy entails in the continuum between waiting for the perfect shot and the spray and pray approach, we can look at the average number of shots fired by each skill combination under the optimal strategy. This is shown in Figure 3.4. (For the outlier with a speed of 2 s and terrible accuracy of 22.6 cm, it is apparently optimal to hold his fire with enough discipline that he doesn't shoot that much before he times out.)

We see a confirmation of the adage that "You can't miss fast enough to win," even in a game where speed outweighs accuracy as the decisive skill. The most competitive strategies in terms of speed and skill hardly waste a shot. However, as shooters get slower or less accurate, their ammunition consumption increases as much as their time required. A shooter with a speed of 1 s and an accuracy of 8 cm can still expect to finish the task in under a minute, much better than not even trying, but can expect to go through close to 30 rounds in that time. An expert walks in and does it with five rounds for five plates in five seconds.

3.2.5 Results: Best strategies

If the best shooters can hold their fire for a near-guaranteed hit, but also have the skill that this doesn't mean holding their fire forever, how long do they have to hold their fire, or rather, what is a plate speed that they are willing to engage? Figure 3.5 shows the expected performance for different maximum accepted plate speeds for shooters of different speeds. As it turns out, and

Figure 3.4: Best strategy shots fired for shooters of various skills

Figure 3.5: Performance depending on willingness to hold fire (accuracy = 4 cm)

Method	Penalty %
fastest	-5.0%
balance	-2.5%
bottommost	-0.8%
random	0.0%
slowest	2.3%
unbalance	3.9%
topmost	9.3%

Table 3.3: Average time penalty of plate selection methods *vs.* random

counterintuitively, for the better shooter it is optimal to be more discriminating and demand a lower plate speed before he engages and then to pick off that slow plate with his quick reaction time. As shooters get slower, they should be less discriminating about plate speed, and a shooter with a speed of 2.0s, thus 0.4s between commitment to fire and impact, is best off with an approach close to spray and pray, firing without regard to plate speed—and bring enough ammunition. This result holds, for roughly competitive shooter speeds and accuracies, for other accuracy values as well.

What plate should the shooter select to fire at next? Table 3.3 shows the average penalty, for shooters using the optimal value of the maximum plate speed cutoff for their speed and accuracy, and where shooter speed and accuracy are competitive by being no worse than 2 s and 8 cm, respectively, incurred from different methods of plate selection, shown against just picking a random plate. Lower and more negative numbers are better. Interestingly, the intuitive approaches of shooting the topmost plate to remove potential energy from the system and of shooting the slowest plate for ease of aiming both incur a penalty over random plate selection.

The most effective method, counterintuitively, appears to be shooting at the fastest-moving plate. Two effects may combine here: On the one hand, removing the fastest plate removes the most kinetic energy from the system. On the other hand, the fastest plate may also tend to be more often on the weighted side of the wheel, so that removing it tends to rebalance the star, making it less chaotic. Specifically aiming to rebalance the star as a plate selection method is the second-most effective, but this strategy comes down to a random selection when the number of remaining plates is not four or three, whereas selecting the fastest plate always tells the shooter which plate to pick, thus combining energy removal and balancing.

In summary, our preliminary strategy recommendation thus is this: A shooter who is just getting good enough for the Death Star to become a surmountable task should shoot in a firm cadence, independent of current plate speeds. As the shooter develops and his reaction time improves, he should increasingly hold his fire and pick moments when the plates get just slow enough that he is almost assured of a hit. It is advisable not to shoot at the topmost or the slowest plates, tempting as they may be, but on the fastest plate. This can intuitively

be memorized as shooting at the plate most remote from the inner arm's pivot point, in that sense the most outside plate, when the star is rotating in the same direction as the inner arm is swinging, and shooting at the most inside plate when the wheel is rotating in the opposite direction of the arm's swing, thus giving an up/down cadence changing focus each time the arm swings left to right or right to left.

A check of this strategy, easier to implement than consciously looking for the fastest plate, will be a good topic for further investigation. It would also make sense to examine whether different strategies are optimal with different numbers of plates remaining. A reasonably quick shooter will shoot off the first plate while the Death Star is still almost at rest. Intuitively, in that case, the topmost plate would be an attractive target to remove the most kinetic energy. The balance-strategy works pretty well despite, in our formulation, only being different from random selection when there are four or three plates remaining, so it may be a good choice for those plate counts. We could then look for an optimal strategy when only two plates are remaining. Another extension would be to expand our assumption of the shooter only being able to hold for linear velocity and to extend it, perhaps such that the shooter will hold for the current circle arc the chosen plate is traveling on.

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Reproducibility

The code package accompanying this paper should run on most modern *nix systems, as documented further in `README.md`, and regenerate this paper as well as additional supporting output, an animation of the Death Star in motion and plots of the double-pendulum map with lossless compression.

System information

Key	Value
OS	macOS 26.0.1 (25.0.0), arm64
CPU	Apple M1 Max
Cores (logical)	10
Cores (physical)	10
Python	3.13.7
Python compiler	Clang 16.0.0 (clang-1600.0.26.6)
Environment	venv: .venv
Quarto	1.8.25
Lua \LaTeX	LuaHB \TeX , Version 1.21.0 (TeX Live 2025)
Timestamp	2025-10-19T21:48:54.520775+00:00

Table 3.4: System information

Python packages

Package	Version	Package	Version	Package	Version
affine	2.4.0	anyio	4.11.0	appnope	0.1.4
argon2-cffi	25.1.0	argon2-cffi-bindings	25.1.0	arrow	1.3.0
astroid	3.3.11	asttokens	3.0.0	async-lru	2.0.5
attrs	25.3.0	babel	2.17.0	beautifulsoup4	4.14.2
bleach	6.2.0	certifi	2025.10.5	cffi	2.0.0
charset-normalizer	3.4.3	comm	0.2.3	contourpy	1.3.3
cycler	0.12.1	debugpy	1.8.17	decorator	5.2.1
defusedxml	0.7.1	dill	0.4.0	executing	2.2.1
fastjsonschema	2.21.2	fonttools	4.60.1	fqdn	1.5.1
graphviz	0.21	h11	0.16.0	httpcore	1.0.9
httplib	0.28.1	idna	3.10	iniconfig	2.1.0
ipykernel	6.30.1	ipython	9.6.0	ipython_pygments_lexers	1.1.1
isoduration	20.11.0	isort	6.1.0	jedi	0.19.2
Jinja2	3.1.6	json5	0.12.1	jsonpointer	3.0.0
jsonschema	4.25.1	jsonschema-specifications	2025.9.1	jupyter-events	0.12.0
jupyter-lsp	2.3.0	jupyter_client	8.6.3	jupyter_core	5.8.1
jupyter_server	2.17.0	jupyter_server_terminals	0.5.3	jupyterlab	4.4.9
jupyterlab_pygments	0.3.0	jupyterlab_server	2.27.3	kiwisolver	1.4.9
lark	1.3.0	llvmlite	0.45.1	MarkupSafe	3.0.3
matplotlib	3.10.6	matplotlib-inline	0.1.7	mccabe	0.7.0
mistune	3.1.4	nbclient	0.10.2	nbconvert	7.16.6
nbformat	5.10.4	nest-asyncio	1.6.0	notebook	7.4.7
notebook_shim	0.2.4	numba	0.62.1	numbakit-ode	0.5
numbalsoda	0.3.4	numpy	2.3.3	numpy-typing-compat	20250818.2.3
optype	0.13.4	packaging	25.0	pandas	2.3.3
pandas-stubs	2.3.2.250926	pandocfilters	1.5.1	parso	0.8.5
pexpect	4.9.0	pillow	11.3.0	pip	25.2
platformdirs	4.4.0	pluggy	1.6.0	prometheus_client	0.23.1
prompt_toolkit	3.0.52	psutil	7.1.0	ptyprocess	0.7.0
pure_eval	0.2.3	pycparser	2.23	Pygments	2.19.2
pylint	3.3.9	pyarsing	3.2.5	pytest	8.4.2
python-dateutil	2.9.0.post0	python-json-logger	3.3.0	pytz	2025.2
PyYAML	6.0.3	pyzmq	27.1.0	referencing	0.36.2
requests	2.32.5	rfc3339-validator	0.1.4	rfc3986-validator	0.1.1
rfc3987-syntax	1.1.0	rpds-py	0.27.1	scipy	1.16.2
scipy-stubs	1.16.2.0	Send2Trash	1.8.3	setuptools	80.9.0
six	1.17.0	sniffio	1.3.1	sounddevice	0.5.2
soupsieve	2.8	stack-data	0.6.3	terminado	0.18.1
tinycss2	1.4.0	tomlkit	0.13.3	tornado	6.5.2
traitlets	5.14.3	types-python-dateutil	2.9.0.20250822	types-pytz	2025.2.0.20250809
typing_extensions	4.15.0	tzdata	2025.2	uri-template	1.3.0
urllib3	2.5.0	wcwidth	0.2.14	webcolors	24.11.1
webencodings	0.5.1	websocket-client	1.8.0	wheel	0.45.1

Table 3.5: Python packages in active environment